

V International Forum on Teacher Education

The Competence-based Approach in Teaching Russian Language in the System of Modern Professional Education for Non-Philologist Students

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Abstract

The article is devoted to one of the topical issues of modern pedagogical science - the competence approach in teaching the Russian language in the frame of modern professional education for non-philology students. The main competence, formed in the process of learning the Russian language is a communicative competence, which is aimed at the development of speech activity of students of non-philological specialties. According to the author of the study, the acquisition of professional communication skills, the use of speech influence techniques, and persuasion is a part and parcel of culture of a non-philologist specialist in the high-tech competitive world. In this regard, the purpose of this work is to create pedagogical conditions that ensure the formation of the communicative competence of non-philology students at the university; the definition of pedagogical learning technologies to improve the culture of verbal communication of future specialists; identification of the professional orientation of psychological and pedagogical knowledge. The practical significance of the problem under study is to improve the quality of professional training of non-philology students; in determining the trajectory of the educational growth of a future highly qualified specialist who is able to reasonably choose language means in his professional activity, adequately implement his communicative intentions in various communication situations, follow the rules of Russian speech etiquette and non-verbal communication.

Keywords: competence-based approach, vocational education, linguodidactics, non-philologist student, communicative competence, Russian language.

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Published by Kazan Federal University and peer-reviewed under responsibility of IFTE-2019 (V International Forum on Teacher Education)

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Introduction

The modern system of professional education at the higher school is directed to the strengthening of practical orientation of training assuming introduction and realization of the competence-based approach. At the present stage of the development of society valuable characteristics of a highly qualified specialist are self-development, self-education, self-design, self-improvement. The competence-based approach is a modern direction of the development of the contents of education as a result of which future experts acquire necessary knowledge and skills, learn to be mobile, constructive, to solve specific tasks and to achieve results.

The question of the competence-based approach in modern linguistic methodologies is relevant. The analysis of scientific and methodical works (Zimnyaya, 2004; Kerimbaeva, 2012; Khutorskoy, 2013; Larionova, Korneyeva, Yusupova, & Latfullina, 2018; Nurullina, Erofeeva, & Usmanova, 2018) shows that the scale of the tasks facing the modern society increases the relevance of the competence-based approach in the system of modern professional education. Due to the new understanding, organization and methodical content of the educational process there appear many questions of teaching Russian to non-philologist students. The solution of the problem of teaching professional communication skills in Russian is carried out in the course of learning the high school discipline "Russian language and the standards of speech".

The practice of teaching Russian language and speech culture shows that non-philology students often face the problem of perception, understanding of scientific information. Work with scientific texts is for students of complex mental activity, including the synthesis and systematization of the knowledge gained by the reader-recipient. In the process of perception of a scientific text, a student may experience difficulties associated with misunderstanding of the semantic content of the text: the reader does not have a good knowledge of existing knowledge, does not understand the meaning of the text due to the presence of a large number of terms, abstract vocabulary, and complex syntactic structures.

Problem Statement

The problem of the current research is the competence-based approach in teaching Russian to non-philologist students. It is known that the essential culture of any expert (philologist and non-philologist) in the hi-tech competitive world is the acquirement of skills of professional communication, using of methods of speech influence and convince. The competence-based approach in teaching Russian to non-philologist students assumes the formation of key competencies the main among which is the communicative competence aimed at the development of speech activity of students of non-philological specialties.

Research Questions

The main attention in the discipline "Russian language and the standards of speech" is paid to the development of knowledge and skills of non-philologist students to choose the language means in the professional activity reasonably; to realize the communicative intentions in various situations of communication adequately; to follow the rules of the Russian speech etiquette and nonverbal communication; to be able to define and eliminate the main speech errors, to make competent, logical and expressive written and oral texts; to annotate and review texts of the scientific style.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to analyze the significance of communicative competence in the process of learning the Russian language and the culture of speech of non-philology students; in the creation of pedagogical conditions that ensure the formation of the communicative competence of students at the university, the motivation to research the characteristics of the scientific text.

The study also considers the problem of the perception and understanding of scientific information by non-philologists; in identifying the professional direction of psychological and pedagogical knowledge, technology of the educational process.

Methods

In the process of forming the communicative competence of non-philology students, an important task is the awareness of future language specialists as a means of communication, a means of understanding the world in a changing economic and socio-cultural situation, expanding the global informatization space. As a result, in the process of teaching the Russian language to non-philology students, we distinguish the following pedagogical technologies: interactive study (interaction with educational material, teacher and students); active learning (solving communicative and extralinguistic problems); textocentric learning (text is an object of language, speech).

Results

Each of the listed technologies occupies an important place in the formation of speech activity of non-philology students. The content of learning the Russian language and speech culture includes different learning activities with language material while working with text: analysis, synthesis, comparison, observation, design, summarizing the language fact under the concept, modification, modeling. Textocentric learning involves teaching students the correct use of language means in accordance with accepted norms of the literary language in all types of speech activity: receptive (listening - reading), productive (speaking - writing).

While working with the scientific text, non-philologists receive information expressed both at the deep level (meaning) and with the help of surface structures (code, means of transmitting meaning). As you know, science, analyzing the laws of the surrounding reality, thinks abstractly, with concepts and categories, and embodies the process of thinking in a logical sequence of judgments and conclusions. Informative richness and evidence, the hierarchy of construction, the generalized abstract nature of presentation, focus on uniform understanding are features of a scientific text, calculated not on emotional-sensual, but on logical perception. The understanding of the scientific text is a complex cognitive activity of the subject, for the effectiveness of which requires a sufficiently high level of development of verbal-analytical, conceptual thinking. The depth of understanding and comprehension of a scientific text depends on the formation of the psychological mechanism for processing semantic information, including the operations of analysis and synthesis, classification, synthesis and abstraction, summarization and development of text meanings.

Taking into account the specifics of a scientific text as a complex semantic-syntactic education, when working with it we identify several key tasks, the solution of which contributes to the development of students' verbal and cognitive activity, the formation of the communicative competence of future specialists. Analysis of the scientific text in the study of the discipline "Russian language and culture of speech" by non-philology students, we begin with identifying the level of development of metalinguistic

reflection, cognitive flexibility in the perception and processing of scientific information. Reflection, as Bogin (1986) said, “is the ability to understand one's understanding and, if necessary, explain the reasons for precisely this, and not another understanding”. Therefore, after reading a small-scale scientific text (we use a fragment of the article by Kasavin (2000) about creativity students are asked to explain the meaning of statements, in case of difficulty to analyze the causes of difficulties arising from the perception of content, and to create an algorithm for overcoming communicative difficulties. We give typical answers of students: “1. Complicated wording, terms. We need to look at the meaning of complicated words in the dictionary. Replace them with simpler synonyms. Put a footnote. 2. Reveal keywords. 3. Complex structure. Select fragments. Split / split complex sentences into several simple ones. / Replace word order. 4. Analyze the structure, remove fragments that do not contain information. 5. Understand the sense relation the text. As we can see, these statements reflect, on the one hand, the process of understanding the information as a whole, which is caused by three types of understanding of the text - semanticizing, cognitive and distributional (Bogin, 1986). On the other hand, they reflect difficulties in the perception of a scientific text due to the complexity of the coded meaning and language code, the limited capabilities of the subject of speech.

The task of the next stage is the formation of communicative and speech competence, which implies the interpretation of the content of the scientific text “for others”, the attitude for dialogue. Interactive interaction is one of the most important features of interactive study. Based on the dialogue, the basic human need for communication and interaction with others is realized, self-awareness, student self-regulation is activated. The essence of interactive learning is the organization of the student's cognitive activity, which makes an individual contribution to the process of retention of material. As a result of interactive learning, knowledge, skills, ideas and experience are exchanged, which contributes to the formation of basic communication skills among non-linguists students.

Depending on the interlocutor, the choice of the optimal method of logical development of the statement as the result of interpretation is carried out. So, for example, if the addressee is a student, the most acceptable way from the point of view of future specialists is an inductive method: from the particular to the logical generalizations, which helps to establish the connection between the existing and acquired knowledge. The choice of the image of the content of the text is carried out through the actualization of personal meanings, reflecting the practical, mental and emotional experience of the speakers. It is these images and their interpretation that become the starting point for disclosing the content of the source text (Nurullina, Ramazanov, & Usmanova, 2018).

In this case, a sufficiently high level of textual analysis is required, which is determined by the readiness for object-oriented and, especially, subject-analytical methods of transmitting information (for example, in the form of the author's analytical commentary); ability to complex transcoding information, to compression, transformation: formulating the statement, students first explicate its nuclear content (anticipating the future semantic integrity of the text), then expand the speech work, creating a complex system of hierarchically related predicates (Sedov, 1999). In some cases, the explanation is accompanied by graphic illustrative material - diagrams, algorithms, drawings. At this stage, students are given another communicative task is to interest students. This allows you to focus on the rhetorical methods of interaction with the audience, necessary for the formation of communicative competence.

The next stage in the development of the necessary verbalization skills is the use of extralinguistic tasks in the practice of teaching active learning related to the creation of communicative text. The communicative text stimulates the activation of the necessary speech skills, motivates the choice of means

of expression, speech tactics of interaction with the addressee of (Butorina, 2018). Text activity aimed at creating a communicative text is designed to determine extralinguistic factors that involve the analysis of the original educational and scientific text, its revision- the interpretation and transformation of the source information. The formation of “communicative competence in creating communicatively significant texts is associated with expanding the genre and thematic repertoire of the writer, learning new speech registers, learning the basics of critical reading and academic writing” (Golovanova, 2017).

One type of creation of a communicative text is the writing by students of non-philologists of the text of the abstract. For the successful creation of the text of the essay, students, of course, must comply with the spelling, punctuation, grammatical norms of the modern Russian literary language. Speech writing is one of the most important rhetorical skills of a speaker. Studying the discipline "Russian language and culture of speech", students acquire the skills of public speaking: they work with scientific literature, make a plan of a speech, write a text, learn estimate their time during a speech. Creating a text of the essay reveals the difficulties associated with the features of perception and processing of scientific information, the formation of analytical skills, and cognitive development of the authors of the texts.

As a result of our experiment, we identified the following difficulties faced by non-philologists in preparing the text of the essay: difficulty in defining the problem indicated in the title of the essay, which leads to the wrong selection of literature, to the expansion or narrowing of the research topic; inability to formulate goals, objectives, summarize the results of the study in the conclusions; violation of the logic of presentation due to the lack of skills among students of the correct isolation in the content blocks of the main, additional and redundant information; incorrect search of the necessary information in the texts to illustrate his statement, to adduce reasons, counterarguments.

When creating a text of the abstract of non-philology students, it is important to teach separating intellectual judgment from emotional, colloquial utterance. The scientific content of the text of the abstract includes representative lexical and communicative units for a scientific discourse: lexemes-terms with scientific content, clichéd, standardized turns of scientific speech, syntactic phrase-models that constitute scientific value. The analysis of the text of the speech of non-philology students revealed the following shortcomings associated with the non-observance of the characteristics of the scientific style: the colloquial, expressive manner of presentation (rhetorical questions) dominates in scientific speech; instead of the pronoun "we" the personal pronoun "I" is used; for the purpose and objectives of the research, the words “learn”, “want to”, “tell” and others are present in the scientific apparatus; there are no meaningful expressions components; speech deficiency (unintentional ellipse, logical and grammatical lacunae) and speech redundancy (tautology and pleonasm, syntactic repetitions) are present.

Conclusion

Thus, the analysis of pedagogical technologies of interactive study, active learning, text-centric learning led to the conclusion that non-philologists students have to work with a scientific text communication difficulties, reducing the culture of scientific speech of future specialists. In the process of learning the Russian language and the culture of speech of non-philology students, it is important to use the system of work for the review process of language material, communication tasks and conversation of a professional orientation. The system of professional education in higher education involves a process of progressive change in the personality of the student under the influence of social influences, the university disciplines studied, and his own activity aimed at self-improvement. This system is aimed at developing the skills of practical application. In addition, as a result of mastering the “Russian language and culture of

speech” discipline, a non-philology student must become a highly erudite specialist who is able to know not only his subject of speech, but also be knowledgeable in the field of literature, art, painting, music, politics, economics native land and other nations.

The formation of the communicative competence of non-philologist students is based taking into account the competence-based approach of teaching languages being claimed in the linguistic didactics which consists in the definition of a trajectory of the educational growth of each student, in the integrated and purposeful impact on the inclinations of the personality capable to show high creativity and motivation in studying the subject.

Acknowledgements

The work is performed according to the Russian Government Program of Competitive Growth of Kazan Federal University.

References

- Bogin, V. G. (1986). *Typology of text understanding*. Kalinin: Kalininskij gosudarstvennyj universitet.
- Butorina, E. P. (2018). *Russian language and culture of speech: a textbook for academic bachelor*. Moscow: YURAJT.
- Golovanova, I. Yu. (2017). Cognitive-psychological aspects of textual methods of learning activities in the process of the formation of communicative competence. *Bulletin of Chelyabinsk State University*, 12(408), 71-75.
- Zimnyaya, I. A. (2004). *Key competencies as an effective target basis of a competence-based approach in education*. Author's version. Moscow: Issledovatel'skij centr problem kachestva podgotovki specialistov.
- Kasavin, I. T. (2000). Space and time: in search of “natural ontology” of knowledge. *Social Sciences and Modernity*, 1, 90-99.
- Kerimbaeva, B. T. (2012). To the question of determining the essence of the concept “competence approach” in the professional training of future specialists. *Basic research*, 3, 581-585.
- Khutorskoy, A. V. (2013). *Competence approach to learning*. Scientific and methodological manual. Moscow: Izdatel'stvo Instituta obrazovaniya cheloveka.
- Larionova, A. A., Korneyeva T. A., Yusupova, Z. F., Latfullina, L. G. (2018). Improving Professional Speech Culture of Teachers of Russian Language and Literature, 8(1), 2315-2318.
- Nurullina, G. M., Ramazanov, R. K., Usmanova, L. A. (2018). Psycholinguistic Aspect of Studying the Text as a Product of Speech Activity. *The Journal of Social Sciences Research*, 1, 113-116
- Nurullina G. M., Erofeeva I. V., Usmanova L. A. (2018). Organization Of Extra-Curricular Activity In The System Of Teacher Professional Training. *The European Proceedings of Social & Behavioural Sciences*, 36, 310-316
- Sedov, K. F. (1999). *The Formation of the Discursive Thinking of a Language Person: Psycho-and Sociolinguistic Aspects*. Saratov: Izdatel'stvo Saratovskogo universiteta.